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TRANSFORMÁCIA KLINICKÝCH LABORATÓRIÍ K DIGITALIZÁCII THE TRANSFORMATION OF CLINICAL LABORATORIES TOWARDS DIGITALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

By their nature, clinical laboratories are places where a huge amount of data is collected. These data represent the treasure of healthcare organizations and with changing perception regarding their nature and utility, laboratories may evolve from simply manufacturing information to a decision engine that drives action across healthcare. To successfully adapt and take advantage of these new circumstances and respond to these new expectations, clinical laboratories need to develop in the direction of digital transformation. Digitalization or digital transformation of clinical laboratories represents a process that involves the use of digital technology to collect data, automate processes, establish trends, and mark better business decisions. The transformation of clinical laboratories towards digitalization requires processes that improve digital maturity. This implies establishing connectivity, end-to-end workflow, and advanced analytical technologies and techniques. The key role in this process belongs to digital technologies, that are moving the focus of laboratory personnel and scientists from routine to more complex and meaningful work. To achieve this goal, they need to be empowered in working with new instruments and software, but without losing the focus on quality. Reducing laboratory errors, eliminating unnecessary testing and challenges of global harmoni-

zation will become main activity of laboratory medicine professionals. Also, demand management and consultations regarding laboratory test results will become the basic components of clinical laboratory workload (Ceriotti 2019). The close collaboration with artificial intelligence experts is needed to develop algorithms using big data obtained through laboratory and other diagnostic processes, which may improve patient care. Strategies leading clinical laboratories through this transformation are not without challenges. They start from resistance of IVD industry and regulatory issues, continue through the lack of trust from patients and medical professionals, to the demand for the new business model that would support it, along with moral and legal uncertainties. These may be resolved with multidisciplinary collaboration, appropriate accreditation, regulatory control, commercialization, knowledge translation, and disruptive innovation (Church and Naugler, 2022). However, to be able to work in digital environment, medical professionals need knowledge about data management and structure and quality of digital data. These should be included in their education, both undergraduate and postgraduate. Also, the key strategy is establishing interoperability, i.e., communication between different information systems, devices, and applications. It requires accessibility to all relevant data, which, on the other hand makes them

more vulnerable to cybersecurity threats and privacy breaches. Therefore, standards are required that will enable clinicians, laboratories, hospitals, pharmacies, and patients to safely share relevant information (MedTech Europe and COCIR, 2021).

Key words: clinical laboratory; digitalization

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